

Challenges of Teaching a Hands-on Virtual Reality Course

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Abstract

Virtual reality, within the realm of computer engineering, possesses a rich historical legacy dating back to the emergence of the first virtual reality headsets in the 1960s. Today, the field has matured significantly, boasting highly sophisticated hardware and software capable of rendering complex 3D simulations. However, teaching virtual reality presents a formidable challenge due to the relentless pace of technological evolution. With new tools and standards emerging regularly, educators face the daunting task of maintaining up-to-date instructional strategies. Traditional teaching resources, such as books, often fall short, particularly in hands-on virtual reality courses, where the techniques for implementing user experiences are in a constant state of flux. Even theoretical content within textbooks may become swiftly outdated, making certain optimizations obsolete as new strategies emerge with remarkable frequency. In this paper, the process of identifying a foundational knowledge base for virtual reality that is less susceptible to obsolescence is elucidated. Strategies for curating and preparing instructional materials for students and offer support mechanisms to address information gaps will be outlined. Despite the rapid evolution of the field, students can successfully engage in the development of sophisticated projects within the realm of virtual reality.

Keywords: Teaching Challenges; Instructional Strategies; Virtual Reality Evolution.

1 Introduction

Since Ivan Sutherland's pioneering contributions to Virtual Reality (VR) in the late 1960s, the field has remained specialized, with few available devices, usually expensive, a small community, and a limited set of standards. However, in the 2010s, Palmer Luckey founded Oculus, introducing a product that was an immediate success: the Rift headset (Tribe & Dr. Sivarethinamohan, 2023). This innovation marked the beginning of a VR revolution, catalyzing the entry of immersive technologies into consumer markets, transforming them into commodity products rather than something only affordable by large companies or research centers, and fueling the growth of what is now a multi-billion-dollar industry (*AR & VR - Worldwide | Statista Market Forecast*, n.d.).

The rapid advancement of virtual reality (VR) technology presents a formidable challenge for educators in this area, relying on traditional educational resources like textbooks, slide presentations, and video content. With an array of vendors, alongside diverse content creation tools including Unity, Godot, Unreal, and various native software development kits (SDKs), the landscape of VR technology is both vast and intricate. These continuous and swift technological evolutions necessitate regular updates to course materials, which struggle to align with the latest software and hardware developments. Educators must navigate this complex ecosystem to effectively incorporate new techniques, optimizations, and solutions into their curriculum, ensuring that their teaching methods are both updated and relevant.

Dynamic course material is proposed to establish a foundational knowledge base in virtual reality (VR) that remains resilient amid rapid technological changes. This course not only introduces essential VR concepts and techniques but also incorporates adaptive learning strategies to continuously integrate the latest advancements in the field, ensuring that students are always at the forefront of VR technology. The use of community resources and artificial intelligence tools is also explored to support and enrich the learning process. Furthermore, the creation of a dynamic learning environment is emphasized, which encourages

students not only to acquire knowledge but also to engage in continuous learning and share their experiences. This approach fosters a collaborative and adaptive educational ecosystem.

In the following sections, there is a discussion on the establishment of development environments for virtual reality, with a detailed curriculum. The paper concludes with our observations, highlighting key insights and outcomes derived from the implementation of these educational strategies.

2 Development Environment for Virtual Reality

Access to VR equipment is crucial in a student's learning journey in modern VR technology. Many traditional VR courses fall short by focusing solely on the theoretical aspects of Virtual Reality as a mere topic in computer graphics (Häfner et al., 2013). This approach can significantly hinder a comprehensive understanding of VR technologies, since it is a complex area, that involves from hardware to software, from programming to designing experiences. Hands-on experience is essential for grasping the complex interplay between software and hardware that VR entails. Ensuring students have the necessary tools to engage directly with VR environments is key to fostering a deeper, more practical mastery of the subject. This document presents the experience of a laboratory, in which VR-ready workstations are provided equipped with Head-Mounted Displays (HMD) to facilitate this endeavor.

For the HMDs, the HTC Vive, a PCVR system (Personal Computer Virtual Reality system) that connects a PC workstation to a Virtual Reality device, was initially utilized. This device was developed through a partnership between Valve and HTC, and launched in 2016 (Lomas, 2016). As a robust PCVR system, the Vive headset must be connected to a computer, typically via cable. While wireless options also exist, they significantly increase the setup's complexity, cost, and add dependencies on additional software and hardware. The reliance on a computer's processing power enables high-performance VR experiences but also introduces potential points of failure in the connections. This often leads to technical issues that require extensive troubleshooting. To overcome the difficulties in both efficiency and reliability, the HTC Vive headsets were upgraded to Meta Quest 2, a standalone VR system. Unlike the PCVR systems, the Meta Quest 2 has a single USB cable for connecting with a PC but can also be connected through conventional Wi-Fi infrastructure. Meta Quest also works without a connection to a computer, which simplifies the setup even more and reduces potential technical issues. This newer system has proven significantly simpler and more user-friendly, greatly improving the accessibility and quality of student projects. Its integrated processing capabilities allow for a seamless VR experience, free from the cumbersome wires and additional hardware requirements of traditional PCVR setups. Figure 1 shows the two virtual reality kits. Notice that the HTC Vive has a larger number of cables and depends on active infrared patterns that must be strategically positioned on the environment, while the Quest 2 is much simpler.

To ensure the students' activities and projects progress smoothly during the academic semester, it is crucial that students have flexibility to access VR equipment, allowing student's access throughout the day, as well as support provided by a laboratory technician. These technicians do more than just oversee the use of the lab, they bring expertise in Virtual Reality development and are readily available to assist students technically. This not only enhances the students' development process but also ensures a seamless and productive learning experience. Their support is vital in helping students overcome technical challenges and in fostering an environment conducive to innovation and learning.

Since this course's inception in the laboratory, back in 2017, a variety of tools and platforms in virtual reality development were actively explored. Initially, the toolkits presented for students included VRTK (VRTK, 2024), an open-source project designed for cross-platform VR development. However, its utility has been diminished over the years. The following main toolkit presented for developing VR project was then Valve's SteamVR,

which, despite its potential, posed increasing challenges due to a lack of comprehensive documentation (Valve, 2024), thereby negatively impacting the learning experience.

Figure 1. Comparison between HTC Vive and Meta Quest 2 Virtual Reality Kits

In response to these challenges, the latest iteration of the course has transitioned to using Unity native XR Interaction Toolkit (XRI) platform (Unity, 2024), with OpenXR development environment (Khronos, 2024), but also the Meta Interaction SDK (Oculus Developers, 2024) for some specific needs. The OpenXR is usually selected for its robust features, extensive support for a wide range of VR hardware, and a growing community that provides well-maintained documentation. Furthermore, understanding the importance of diverse skill sets and personal interests, students are encouraged to explore and choose alternative tools such as Godot or Unreal Engine. This flexible approach not only enhances their technical proficiency but also allows students to customize their learning experience to align with their future career goals or personal interests in VR development.

3 Ensuring Foundational Learning

One of the first challenges in virtual reality (VR) education is that traditional teaching resources, such as textbooks and lecture materials, often struggle to keep pace with the rapid evolution of VR technology. This discrepancy can lead to significant gaps in students' understanding and proficiency, undermining their ability to adapt to innovative technologies, a skill essential for success in the field.

To address these challenges, community-generated content was incorporated into course material, including freely available videos, official and unofficial tutorials, and forum threads. By actively curating these resources, a rapid iteration and timely updates to our course content is maintained. This strategy not only keeps our course material aligned with the latest developments in VR but also cultivates a lifelong learning mindset among students. Such an approach is critical in preparing them for the continual challenges and opportunities they will encounter throughout their careers. In the latest version of this course, a sequence of videos from the YouTuber Valem was used (Valem, 2024). While some educators might criticize this method, the fact is that students can follow the instructions while simultaneously understanding technical concepts. Students are much more comfortable watching videos to learn the practical aspects of virtual reality and the tools used. Although written material is also provided to explain the tools, students were more effective when using videos.

Furthermore, it is essential to look beyond the practical implementation of virtual reality experiences to address the foundational building blocks of the technology and its context. The proposed curriculum, therefore, includes a range of fundamental topics such as types of tracking, stereoscopy techniques, and other core theoretical principles. These lectures are designed to ensure that students not only understand but also connect with the VR frameworks. For an overview of these lectures and their specific content, please refer to Table 1.

Finally, when examined the definition of a Virtual Reality (VR) experience, it aligns closely with the well-known framework of the '3I's': Immersion, Interaction, and Imagination. Immersion provides users with a convincing, all-encompassing virtual environment that often transcends physical reality. Interaction allows users to manipulate and engage with this environment in intuitive ways, further enhancing the sense of presence within the virtual world. Lastly, Imagination powers the creation and expansion of these environments, pushing the boundaries of what is possible and enabling experiences that are not feasible in the physical world. Together, these elements form the core of what makes VR a uniquely transformative technology (Burdea & Coiffet, 2003).

To facilitate this learning progression, the implemented VR course is structured around three progressive projects, each one designed to deepen students understanding and skills within the realms of both virtual and augmented realities. These projects incrementally build on each other, ensuring that with each step, students are better prepared to work in the intricate demands of VR and AR technologies.

The proposed learning path is inspired in the Challenge-Based Learning (CBL) approach, where in this case a progressive path of knowledge acquisition in VR development is established, ensuring that students achieve a comprehensive understanding of core virtual reality topics. This method promotes active problem-solving and real-world application, allowing learners to deeply engage with the material while developing critical thinking skills. As they progress through increasingly complex challenges, students not only solidify their grasp of foundational principles but also enhance their ability to creatively apply this knowledge in diverse scenarios.

Table 1. Planned classes for Virtual Reality Course.

Class #	Content	Discussion
1	Experience in Virtual Reality	Familiarization with Virtual Reality devices, XR Discussion
2	Developing for Virtual Reality	Familiarize with the headsets, and start the first project
Project 1: Escape Room		
3	Introduction to Virtual Reality	An overall of the basic aspects of Virtual Reality
4	Head-Mounted-Display	Main details of the modern Virtual Reality headsets
5	Sensor Tracking	Tracking system and integrations in virtual environments
6	Development Standards	Main standards for Virtual Reality development
7	Depth and Perception	Stereoscopy, Binocular disparity, Field of View
8	Virtual Reality Applications	Areas where virtual reality has supported users
9	Experience Design	Design strategies to create a better experience
Project 2: AR Project		
10	Augmented Reality	Operation of Augmented Reality Systems
11	Forms of 3D Interaction	Interaction devices, force return
12	Virtual Menus	Discussions on forms of virtual menus, Heads Up Displays
13	3D Physical Simulations	Interaction Issues, Particles, Ray Casting
14	Avatars	Kinematics Inverse, Deformable Meshes, Animations
15	Studio Class	Project Development
16	Spatialized 3D Audio	Development of scenarios with spatialized audio
Project 3: Final Project		
17	Metaverse	How to participate in virtual environments
18	Distributed Virtual Environments	How to synchronize distributed content
19	Skybox and 360 Degree Photos	360-degree media captures
20	Data Entry System	Eye-tracking, Leap-motion, Virtual Reality Gloves
21	Level of Detail Control	Include Level of Detail Control (LOD)
22	Locomotion	Teleportation and tracked displacement systems
23	3D Modeling	3D modeling shapes and tools
24	Phasic System	Return of force, vibrations
25	Publishing WEB VRML/X3D	Presentation of x3d format for web.
26	3D tracking by cameras	Capture position and movement by camera systems
27	Final Demo	Final Demo

3.1 Projects

3.1.1 Escape Room

The first course project serves as an introduction to virtual reality, challenging students to create their own Escape Room game (Figure 2). Escape room games are highly popular in VR, comprising interactive puzzle environments where players are 'locked' in a room or a series of rooms. To progress and ultimately escape, players must meticulously explore their surroundings, gather distinct items, and solve a sequence of puzzles using clues from the environment. This genre effectively leverages the immersive capabilities of virtual reality to enhance problem-solving experiences, deeply engaging students and making them feel an integral part of the complex scenarios they develop.

Despite its perceived simplicity, this project introduces several fundamental concepts critical to virtual reality applications. It illuminates discussions on environment scale and perception, the clarity of interactive elements, and the use of spatial, diegetic, and non-diegetic 3D user interfaces. Moreover, it explores various techniques of player movement, such as teleportation, among others. This project not only teaches technical skills but also fosters a deeper understanding of how VR environment's function and how they influence user interaction.

Figure 2. Escape Room Projects made by the students¹

3.1.2 AR Project.

In the second project, the focus shifts to augmented reality (AR), enabling students to explore a different technology within the extended reality (XR) spectrum. This project introduces multiple AR techniques, such as marker tracking with ARUco markers (Garrido-Jurado et al., 2016), other marker systems, markerless techniques, and geospatial markers. Advanced topics like simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) (Gaia et al, 2023), image recognition, and the integration of AR with IoT devices are also covered, providing a broad view of AR's versatility and practical applications.

Students are not required to use specific technology, however, they commonly select the Vuforia Engine (PTC, 2024), a widely used augmented reality software development kit known for its user-friendly interface and rapid results. Vuforia's advanced computer vision capabilities allow for the real-time recognition and tracking of images and objects, making it an ideal choice for developers seeking to create immersive and interactive AR experiences efficiently. This technology supports students in quickly transitioning from concept to execution,

¹ Top Left: <https://gubebra.itch.io/hypostatize> Top Right: <https://lidiaacd.itch.io/orbsescape>
Bottom Left: <https://mikomoares.itch.io/horizontal-tower> Bottom Right: <https://siredington.itch.io/escape-alien>

significantly enhancing their learning process through practical application. Overall, this project is designed to familiarize students with AR's unique characteristics and potential applications, encouraging them to explore how AR technology can be seamlessly integrated into real-world scenarios and thus broadening their technical repertoire (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Augmented Reality project with image as marker

3.1.3 Final Project

The final project in our curriculum grants students the autonomy to fully apply the breadth of knowledge they have acquired throughout the course. In this project, students are tasked with defining a unique theme that serves as the foundation for their virtual reality (VR) creation (Figure 4). They then engage in a weekly scrum-based (Jurado-Navas, 2017) approach, which facilitates iterative planning, development, and refinement phases, mimicking real-world software development cycles. This method not only reinforces project management and teamwork skills but also helps students stay aligned with their project goals and timelines.

As they progress, students are required to draw upon their full range of VR development skills, from conceptualizing the initial idea to implementing and refining the final product. This phase of the course is critical as it challenges them to synthesize and apply everything they have learned in a practical setting. They must navigate the complexities of VR design, including user interaction, environmental design, and the integration of advanced VR features to create compelling, immersive experiences. By the end of this project, students are expected to deliver a complete VR experience, demonstrating their competence and innovation in crafting engaging virtual environments that are both functional and imaginative.

Figure 4. Final Projects made by students²

² Top Left: <https://anaclaracf.itch.io/mini-golf-vr> Top Right: <https://sirjohwilliam.itch.io/quiddich-harry> Bottom: <https://gubebra.itch.io/mirage>

3.2 The Metaverse Experience

Defining the Metaverse remains a challenging endeavor in today's rapidly evolving topic (Ritterbusch, 2023). By defining the metaverse as a collective virtual shared space which is persistent and online that facilitates continuous and seamless interactions among users within a computer-generated environment. Our course focused on the available metaverse platforms on the market.

In addition to the core projects, previous versions of the course included a fourth project aimed at applying the skills developed to create an experience within the Metaverse. However, this project was discontinued due to several challenges, particularly related to platform selection. Among the platforms considered was Meta Horizons, a well-known but closed platform for content creators at the time of our evaluation. Another potential platform, VRChat, while popular, requires creators to earn 'trust' through prolonged engagement (VRChat, 2024), which was impractical for a time-bound academic project. Microsoft's AltspaceVR was another viable option until its discontinuation in early 2024 (AltspaceVR Team, 2023). Lastly, NEOS VR was evaluated but found to be too unstable for our needs. Due to these complications, it was decided to focus on the final project, which allows for a broader application of VR development skills without the constraints of existing Metaverse platforms.

Figure 5: Project of virtual environment in the AltspaceVR platform

4 Results and Observations

The emphasis on hands-on experience with a variety of VR systems has been crucial in deepening students' understanding of VR technology. By engaging directly with advanced tools and platforms, students gain a comprehensive appreciation of the complex technologies that underpin modern VR systems. This exposure not only fosters a deeper understanding but also encourages innovation within this rapidly evolving field. Moreover, by transitioning to more reliable VR hardware like Meta Quest 2 and streamlining the development environments, the frequency and severity of hardware-related disruptions was significantly reduced. This update to standalone VR systems has not only decreased the time students spend troubleshooting technical issues but also enhanced their ability to maintain a steady workflow. As a result, students can focus more on developing complex and high-quality projects, leading to the creation of richer, more engaging VR experiences. The seamless integration of these systems into our course framework allows creativity and technical skills to flourish, underscoring our commitment to providing a robust educational experience unimpeded by technical malfunctions.

These observations collectively highlight how improvements in VR equipment access and system reliability have not only enriched the learning environment but also broadened the scope of what students can achieve. As a result, students get well-prepared to lead and innovate in the field of virtual reality, equipped with both a solid understanding of technology and the capability to apply their skills in complex, real-world scenarios.

5 Conclusion

The field of virtual reality is evolving at an unprecedented pace, what makes necessary to rebuild the practical activities material, every semester, making the task of keeping in level with daily updates and changes akin to the labors of Sisyphus. The industry is entering an era where Virtual Reality technology is beginning to stabilize, marked by developments such as the evolution of the OpenXR standard, which reflects the maturing nature of the medium. By immersing students in the fundamental concepts of virtual reality and encouraging them to freely explore various tools and ideas, fostering an educational environment that not only facilitates interaction with innovative technology but also enhances learning through experiential engagement. This approach cultivates the essential skill of 'learning to learn,' empowering students to adapt and thrive in dynamic technological landscapes.

The word 'challenge' was used in several contexts in this paper. The first is the challenge of keeping a virtual reality course updated amidst the constant evolution of the field. Although Challenge-Based Learning (CBL) is not the focus of this paper, this is a strategy employed in some projects to motivate students to learn a new area or topic by posing a challenge they must overcome. Finally, students were motivated to create applications, usually games, that present real challenges for their end users, the players. In summary, Virtual Reality poses numerous challenges.

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